

UV-C CABINET

QUESTIONS FOR IMPLEMENTATION

To be discussed and answered by hospital teams prior to implementation.

1. PRE-IMPLEMENTATION PLANNING

PLANNING:

- Is there a need for N95 or surgical mask decontamination and reuse?
- What is the regulatory approval needed to start using the UVC cabinet? Has this been obtained?
- Who will provide ongoing technical & engineering support?
- Who will make up the hospital-based UVC team?
- What is the anticipated number of masks needed to be reprocessed in an average 24hr period?
- Who is tracking the N95 supply and issuing new masks?
- What is the maximum number of reprocessing cycles per mask?

STAFFING & TRAINING:

- Who will be assigned to operate the UVC cabinet?
- How many staff will be assigned per shift and how long will shifts be?
- How will staff be trained & certified? How long and who will conduct training?
- How will reprocessing staff PPE be allocated for each shift? What happens if staff PPE is not available?

2. UV-C CABINET OPERATION PLANNING

SETUP:

- Where is the physical space allocated for the chamber?
- Is there space designated for contaminated mask intake, reprocessing area, and clean area?
- Are there carts and transportation bins that are breathable for redistributing processed masks?
- Is the power supply adequate? If not, is access to a generator available for use of the cabinet?
- What working hours will the cabinet operate?

MAINTENANCE:

- Where will backup supplies (bulbs, storage containers, disinfectant) be kept and who will have access?
- How will new bulbs be obtained if they burn out?
- What is the routine maintenance plan and who can be called for emergency repairs?
- Will there be routine quality checks? How will these be done - UVC dosimetry or biologic indicators?

3. DECONTAMINATION PROCESS

MASK REPROCESSING:

(DROP OFF, DECONTAMINATION, PICKUP)

- How will masks be labeled?
- Who will collect and return masks from each clinical care unit?
- Will damaged or discarded masks be documented?
- How will the decontamination cycle be timed & monitored?
- How will UVC dose be quantified and confirmed? At each cycle or intermittently?
- What safety measures are in place for protecting staff from UVC exposure?
- How will straps be decontaminated?
- What will indicate the number of cycles and inspection after decon?
- How will masks be stored and returned to the original user?

SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT:

- What type of containers will be used for storage and transport of masks?
- How will materials be ordered and financed when additional supplies are needed?
 - Storage containers:
 - Disinfectant solution & wipes:
 - Labels, markers, logbook paper: